

ISic3418

I.Sicily inscription 3418

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

limestone

Object

tabula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Hypogeum XI, Capuccini catacombs

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Paolo Orsi

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI178075

1. Εἰρήνην νύμφην
2. ὤδε κέῖται.
3. κατὰ τοῦ μυστηρίου
4. οὐ οὖν τούτου μή τ-
5. ἰς ὤδε ἀνύξη.
- 6.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645619

EDCS 38000214

PHI 178075

Bibliography

Noy, D. 1993. Jewish inscriptions of Western Europe. Cambridge. At no.151

Frey, J.-B. 1936-1952. Corpus Inscriptionum Iudaicarum: recueil des inscriptions juives qui vont du IIIe siècle avant Jésus-Christ au VIIe siècle de notre ère.

Vatican City. At 1.651

Orsi, P. 1900. Nuovi ipogei di sètte cristiane e giudaiche ai Cappuccini in Siracusa. *Römische Quartalschrift für christliche Alterthumskunde und für Kirchengeschichte*. 14: 187-209. At 194-197

Feissel, D. 1981. Notes d'épigraphie chrétienne (V). *Bulletin de Correspondance Hellénique*. 105: 483-497. At 486

Robert, L. 1946. Un corpus des inscriptions juives. *Hellenica*. 3: 90-108. At 98

Licensed under a Creative

Commons-Attribution 4.0 licence.

Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-23): ISic3418. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4388540>